

QUALITY OF LIFE OF CHILDREN WITH PRIMARY HYPERPARATHYROIDISM AFTER PARATHYROIDECTOMY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14022675>

Abstract. *The aim of the study was to analyze the quality of life of patients with primary hyperparathyroidism (PHPT) in the late postoperative periods. The study involved 60 patients who, depending on the form of primary hyperparathyroidism, were divided into 3 groups. The survey was conducted using a short quality of life questionnaire (SF-36) before surgery and in the late postoperative period. The data obtained show that the indicators of the quality of life in the postoperative period increase in all groups of patients.*

Keywords: *hyperparathyroidism, children, parathyroidectomy.*

Relevance. Health-related quality of life can be considered as an integral characteristic of the physical, mental and social functioning of a healthy and sick person, based on his subjective perception. In addition, the patient's quality of life is an important criterion for determining the effectiveness of treatment in clinical trials. Assessment of the quality of life is an important indicator, including the clinical and psychological status of the patient before the start of treatment, during the treatment process and after its completion [2,11]. The study of the quality of life makes it possible to accurately describe and measure those disorders that occur during the development of the disease and rehabilitation, especially in the case of such a serious disease as primary hyperparathyroidism [1,3,4,6]. Primary hyperparathyroidism (PHPT) is a disease that develops as a result of primary damage to the parathyroid glands (PTH). Changes are caused by the development of adenoma, hyperplasia or malignancy, which leads to overproduction of parathyroid hormone (PTH) and is manifested by impaired calcium and phosphorus metabolism, damage to bone tissue and (or) internal organs (primarily kidneys and gastrointestinal tract), emotional and mental disorders [1, 4, 5,15]. With the onset of PHPT in childhood and adolescence, when there is an active growth and formation of the skeleton, the bone manifestations of the disease come to the fore [3,5] and can cause the child's disability. The first specialists to whom children and parents turn, as a rule, are district pediatricians, rheumatologists, orthopedists, traumatologists and gastroenterologists. Due to the fact that PHPT in childhood is extremely rare and pediatricians' knowledge about this disease is insufficient, diagnostic errors are possible, leading to a late diagnosis. To date, due to the widespread use of biochemical screening tests, the detection rate of PHPT has improved, according to the data on appeal in our country, there is a clear tendency to an increase in the number of patients, both in adults and children. [4,10]. In the case of the bone form of the disease, most often patients with PHPT complain of pain emanating from the musculoskeletal system, pain when walking, a change in gait, and increased fatigue even during daily work. In the visceral form, such target organs are most often affected as the kidneys with the development of urolithiasis, the stomach and duodenum with the development of ulcerative changes, the pancreas with the development of chronic and often acute recurrent pancreatitis, the gallbladder with the development of calculous cholecystitis. The most severe clinical

manifestations of the disease are found in patients with a mixed form of pathology [1,3,6, 7,9]. Surgical treatment is the radical and most effective method of treating PHPT [7, 8].

According to a number of studies, it has been shown that parathyroidectomy (PTE) leads to an improvement in the quality of life of patients with PHPT [1,6,13,15]. The use of information obtained directly from the patient in the analysis of the clinical manifestations of the disease and the assessment of the dynamics of symptoms in the course of treatment contributes to the implementation of a patient-centered approach in the management of patients with PHPT. Currently, minimally invasive, less traumatic methods of surgical intervention are being actively developed and implemented. These techniques allow minimizing the surgical access, the presence and size of postoperative scars, accelerating the operation time itself, and reducing the negative impact of anesthesia on the patient [8]. Assessment of the quality of life before and after surgical treatment with PHPT can be used for a comprehensive assessment of the effect of therapy, as well as for monitoring the patient's condition after surgery, including in real clinical practice. In this regard, it seems relevant to monitor the quality of life and symptoms in patients with PHPT using standardized questionnaires.

Purpose of the study. To conduct a comparative analysis of the quality of life of patients with primary hyperparathyroidism in the late postoperative period, depending on the type of forms of primary hyperparathyroidism.

Material and research methods.

Our study assessed the quality of life of patients with primary hyperparathyroidism. The study assembly consisted of 60 children with primary hyperparathyroidism who were treated in the departments of pediatric endocrinology and endocrine surgery of the Republican Specialized Scientific Practical Medical Center of Endocrinology of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the period from 2010 to 2020. According to the forms of primary hyperparathyroidism, the patients were divided into groups:

1. Bone form of the disease occurred in 20 cases. The median age was 10.4 years and 35% of them were girls.
2. Visceral form - in 20 cases. The median age was 7.3 years old and 30% of them were girls.
3. Mixed - in 20 cases. The median age was 10.5 years and 35% of them were girls.

The follow-up period after surgery ranged from 1 to 10 years. All respondents were interviewed using a short quality of life questionnaire (SF-36) in the late postoperative period (from 1 to 10 years after surgery). The SF-36 questionnaire (Short Form Medical Outcomes Study, J. E. Ware, 1993) is widely used in both population and special studies [12,13,14]. Translation into Russian, approbation of the technique was carried out by the Institute of Clinical and Pharmacological Research (St. Petersburg). The SF-36 questionnaire was normalized for the general population in the United States and representative samples in Australia, France and Italy. In the USA and European countries, studies of individual populations were carried out and results were obtained according to the norms for the healthy population and for groups of patients with various chronic diseases [9, 11]. The 36 items on the questionnaire are grouped into eight scales: physical functioning, role-playing activity, bodily pain, general health, vitality, social functioning, emotional state, and mental health. The scores on each scale vary between 0 and 100, with 100 representing overall health, and all scales form two scores: mental and physical well-being. The results are presented in the form of scores on 8 scales, designed in such a way that a higher score

indicates a higher level of QoL. The following indicators were quantitatively assessed: 1. Physical Functioning (PF), reflecting the degree to which the physical condition limits the performance of physical activities (self-care, walking, climbing stairs, carrying weights, etc.). Low indicators on this scale indicate that the patient's physical activity is significantly limited by the state of his health. 2. Role-Physical Functioning (RP) influencing daily role-playing activities (work, daily duties). Low scores on this scale indicate that daily activities are significantly limited by the patient's physical condition. 3. Intensity of pain (Bodily pain - BP) and its effect on the ability to carry out daily activities, including work around the house and outside the home. Low scores on this scale indicate that pain significantly limits the patient's activity. 4. General health (GH) - assessment of patients' state of health at the moment and the prospects for treatment. The lower the score on this scale, the lower the health score. 5. Vitality (VT) - implies feeling full of strength and energy, or, on the contrary, exhausted. Low scores indicate patient fatigue, decreased vitality. 6. Social Functioning (SF) - defined by the degree to which a physical or emotional state limits social activity (communication). Low scores indicate a significant limitation of social contacts, a decrease in the level of communication due to a deterioration in the physical and emotional state. 7. Role-Emotional (RE) functioning involves an assessment of the degree to which the emotional state interferes with the performance of work or other daily activities (including a large expenditure of time, a decrease in the volume of work, a decrease in its quality, etc.). Low scores on this scale are interpreted as a limitation in performing daily work due to a deterioration in the emotional state. 8. Mental Health (MH) - characterizes mood, depression, anxiety, general indicator of positive emotions. Low rates indicate the presence of depressive, anxious experiences, mental distress [10]. According to Kenneth Brito et al. [6], the changes achieved by parathyroidectomy are clinically significant with a difference in quality of life indicators of at least 5 points.

This value formed the basis for the interpretation of the data obtained. The study was carried out in two stages. At the first stage, we assessed the quality of life of patients in each of the selected groups 6 months after surgery and performed a comparative analysis of the data obtained. At the second stage, we compared the indicators of the quality of life of patients 12 months after the operation. At the third stage, we carried out a comparative analysis of the data obtained in each of the selected groups. Based on the results of the survey, an electronic database was formed. Statistical processing was carried out using the applied software package "Statsoft (USA) Statistica", 8.0.

Quantitative parameters are presented as median (Me) and interquartile range (25th (LQ) - lower quartile and 75th (UQ) - upper quartile). A nonparametric method of statistical research was used: the Wilcoxon test (to analyze the differences between two dependent groups in terms of quantitative characteristics).

To compare more than two independent groups on a quantitative basis, the Kruskal - Wallis test was used, to compare two independent groups on a quantitative basis, the MannWhitney U-test. The presence of a relationship between the studied parameters was carried out using the correlation analysis according to the Spearman method. The critical level of significance of the null statistical hypothesis was taken equal to or less than 0.05.

Results and discussion.

At the research stage, we asked the patients to evaluate the indicators of the quality of life after the operation. The results of a comparative analysis of the quality of life of patients of each of the selected groups after surgery after 1 year are shown in the (table 1.)

Table 1. Quality of life indicators (SF-36) of patients 1 year after surgery (Me (25%; 75%).

QOL scale	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	H	P
General Health	39 [30; 50]	43,5 [34; 50]	43 [34; 52]	2,712	0,258
Physical Functioning	43 [32; 53]	49,5 [30; 56]	43 [35; 52]	0,493	0,781
Role-Physical	40 [30; 55]	40,5 [30; 52]	44,5 [32; 55]	0,696	0,706
Role-Emotional	43 [22; 47]	43,5 [36; 60]	42,5 [30; 52]	2,938	0,230
Social Functioning	40 [33; 45]	30,5 [20; 46]	35 [26; 44]	2,294	0,318
Bodily Pain	41 [26; 50]	36 [28; 51]	40 [30; 52]	0,857	0,652
Vitality	43 [30; 50]	46,5 [27; 57]	41 [28; 53]	0,415	0,813
Mental Health	42 [38; 46]	46 [33; 55]	38 [26; 55]	1,049	0,592
PH	39 [30; 50]	43,5 [34; 50]	43 [34; 52]	2,712	0,258
MH	43 [32; 53]	49,5 [30; 56]	43 [35; 52]	0,493	0,781

When analyzing the differences in groups, depending on the form of pathology, statistically significant differences were revealed in terms of Social Functioning ($H = 8.455$; $p = 0.037$ Kruskal-Wallis test). When conducting a paired test, it was found that differences on this scale exist between bone and visceral forms of the disease (Mann-Whitney U-test, $U = 122.0$; $Z = -2.477$; $p = 0.01$), as well as between mild and visceral forms (Mann-Whitney U-test, $U = 174.0$; $Z = -2.048$; $p = 0.04$). No differences were found between other forms (Mann-Whitney U-test, $p > 0.05$).

Table 2. Spearman's rank correlations of QOL data and blood serum biochemical parameters.

QOL scale	Ca		Ca 2+		PTH level	
	Rs	p	Rs	p	Rs	p
General Health	0.030644	0.799	-0.120400	0.284	0.007008	0.947
Physical Functioning	-0.105010	0.383	-0.055594	0.622	0.026965	0.800
Role-Physical	-0.052286	0.664	-0.007846	0.944	-0.072114	0.499
Role-Emotional	0.097317	0.419	0.249678	0.024*	-0.019886	0.852
Social Functioning	0.113164	0.347	-0.070453	0.531	-0.000190	0.998
Bodily Pain	-0.249137*	0.036	-0.100345	0.372	0.000235	0.998
Vitality	0.224036	0.060	0.101702	0.366	-0.067725	0.525
Mental Health	-0.028391	0.814	-0.031084	0.782	-0.084550	0.428
PH	-0.246767*	0.038	-0.073733	0.512	-0.020167	0.850
MH	0.187478	0.117	-0.076015	0.500	-0.067046	0.530

* — $p < 0.05$

When analyzing the correlation dependences of QOL indicators with the level of PTH, total and ionized calcium in blood serum 1 year after the operation, the following regularities were obtained: an inverse relationship of the weak strength of the total calcium level with indicators of Bodily Pain and PH was revealed: $rs = -0.249$; $p = 0.036$ and $rs = -0.247$; $p = 0.038$, respectively. There was also a weak strength inverse relationship between the Role Emotional index and ionized calcium ($rs = -0.249$; $p = 0.0245$). No statistically significant correlations between the level of PTH in blood serum were found with any indicator of QOL (Table 2).

The results of a comparative analysis of the quality of life of patients in each of the selected groups in the period 10 years after surgery are shown in (Table 3).

Table 3. Indicators of quality of life (SF-36) of patients in the late postoperative period (after 10 years) (Me (25%; 75%))

QOL scale	Group 1 (n =20)	Group 2 (n =20)	Group 3 (n =20)	H	P
General Health	39 [30; 50]	43,5 [34; 50]	43 [34; 52]	2,712	0.006
Physical Functioning	43 [32; 53]	49,5 [30; 56]	43 [35; 52]	0,493	0.01
Role-Physical	40 [30; 55]	40,5 [30; 52]	44,5 [32; 55]	0,696	0.706
Role-Emotional	43 [22; 47]	43,5 [36; 60]	42,5 [30; 52]	2,938	0.230
Social Functioning	40 [33; 45]	30,5 [20; 46]	35 [26; 44]	2,294	0.318
Bodily Pain	41 [26; 50]	36 [28; 51]	40 [30; 52]	0,857	0.652
Vitality	43 [30; 50]	46,5 [27; 57]	41 [28; 53]	0,415	0.813
Mental Health	42 [38; 46]	46 [33; 55]	38 [26; 55]	1,049	0.001
PH	43 [37; 45]	45 [41; 48]	47 [43; 50]	8,984	0.011
MH	42 [38; 44]	44 [40; 46]	41 [37; 48]	2,065	0.01

Late postoperative period: General Health (Mann-Whitney U-test, $U = 454.5$; $Z = -3.813$; $p = 0.000137$); Role-Physical Functioning (Mann-Whitney U-test, $U = 596.5$; $Z = -2.598$; $p = 0.00939$); Role-Emotional (Mann-Whitney U-test, $U = 429.0$; $Z = -4.031$; $p = 0.000056$); Bodily pain (Mann-Whitney U-test, $U = 665.0$; $Z = -2.011$; $p = 0.044$); Vitality (Mann-Whitney U-test, $U = 663.5$; $Z = -2.024$; $p = 0.043$), as well as PH (Mann-Whitney U-test, $U = 573.0$; $Z = -2.799$; $p = 0.005129$).

During the second stage of the study, we compared the quality of life of patients in each of the selected groups 1 year and 10 years after surgery. In the general cohort of the study, statistically significant differences were revealed for all studied scales (Table 4).

Table 4. Median values of quality of life (SF-36) of patients with long-term outcomes after parathyroidectomy.

QOL scale	1 year after surgery	10 years after surgery		T	Z	p
General Health	52 [42; 60]	65.0 [55; 75]	+13,4	423.0	6.395	0.000001
Physical Functioning	54.5 [42; 65]	71.0 [60; 80]	+16,4	402.9	6.395	0.000001
Role-Physical	50.5 [40; 63]	63.0 [50; 75]	+12,7	683.1	5.407	0.000001
Role-Emotional	62.5 [50; 72]	67.0 [67; 100]	+4,8	528.9	5.509	0.000001
Social Functioning	45.5 [36; 55]	50.0 [45; 63]	+4,8	659.1	4.924	0.000001
Bodily Pain	50.0 [38; 62]	61.0 [45; 73]	+10,8	579.3	5.292	0.000001
Vitality	53.5 [37; 61]	60.0 [50; 75]	+6,5	976.7	3.847	0.000119
Mental Health	52.0 [43; 64]	68.0 [56; 76]	+16	486.7	5.874	0.000001
PH	39.2 [35; 42]	44.6 [40; 48]	+5,6	518.9	6.150	0.000001
MH	38.4 [36; 43]	42.4 [38; 46]	+4,2	605.3	5.808	0.000001

The greatest differences were noted in terms of Physical Functioning, General Health, Mental Health, Role-Physical, and Bodily Pain. These scales characterize both the physical and

mental well-being of the respondents. At the same time, the lowest indices (+5.6 and +4.2) were found when comparing the PH and MN domains, respectively, which characterize the general state of physical and emotional health.

Group 1 showed statistically significant differences in the periods according to the questionnaire scales: General Health (Wilcoxon Matched Pairs Test, $T = 91.5$; $Z = 2.725$; $p = 0.006$), Physical Functioning (Wilcoxon Matched Pairs Test, $T = 111.5$; $Z = 2.489$; $p = 0.0128$), Mental Health (Wilcoxon Matched Pairs Test, $T = 64.5$; $Z = 3.154$; $p = 0.00161$) and MH (Wilcoxon Matched Pairs Test, $T = 112.0$; $Z = 2.478$; $p = 0.0132$) (Figure 2).

In group 2, significant improvement in quality of life was observed in the RolePhysical (+17.5), Bodily Pain (+16.0), and Mental Health (+17.5) domains; moderate - General Health (+12.5), Physical Functioning (+10.5) and Role Emotional (+14.5); minor - Social Functioning (+9.5) and Vitality (+8.5).

In group 3, significant changes were observed in the following QOL indicators: General Health (+17), Bodily Pain (+17), Physical Functioning (+22), Role-Physical (+20.5) and Mental Health (+20); moderate - for the Role-Emotional (+12.5) and Vitality (+11.5) domains. Minor changes were observed in the Social Functioning column (+5).

Conclusion.

1. Performing parathyroidectomy statistically and clinically significantly improves the quality of life of patients with PHPT ($p < 0.00001$), regardless of the access used and the type of anesthesia.

2. A clinically significant increase in the quality of life indicators of patients in the study groups in the postoperative period (after 1 year) was established for all SF domains -36, except for the Role-Emotional and Role-Physical indicators in group 1.

3. When analyzing the correlation dependences of QOL indicators with the level of PTH, total and ionized serum calcium 1 year after the operation, statistically significant correlations of the level of PTH in blood serum were not established with any QOL indicator.

4. Statistically significant differences were revealed for all studied scales in the late postoperative period (after 10 years), compared with the indicators of the postoperative period 1 year after surgery.

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